

NOTES

TABLE

Sample No.	Amount of MgCO ₃ (mg/lit)	Amount of Ca(OH) ₂ (mg/lit)	Turbidity	Before Coagulation			After Coagulation			
				pH	Hardness	Alkalinity	Turbidity	pH	Hardness	Alkalinity
1.	13.3	10.7	30	7.5	32.68	19.89	3	7.7	24.88	29.95
2.	20.75	18.6	42	7.5	30.50	21.32	2	8.0	56.63	52.02
3.	16.60	15.0	28	7.4	62.66	41.31	3	7.8	48.90	49.73
4.	18.30	10.7	31	7.6	56.63	55.09	2	7.9	60.99	64.27

Hardness and Alkalinity in mg/lit. of CaCO₃

MgCO₃ in the presence of lime is converted into sparingly soluble Mg(OH)₂ which takes the fine particles in suspension down with it.

Dosage of MgCO₃ required with different characteristics of water have been tabulated¹.

In the present work cyclic coagulation using MgCO₃ was tried on surface waters collected from different ponds used exclusively for potable purposes by the public of Karaikudi. The hardness, pH, alkalinity as well as turbidity were determined both before and after coagulation for each sample. The dosage of MgCO₃ as also the relative amounts of MgCO₃ and Ca(OH)₂ were optimised so as to reduce the residual turbidity to the minimum possible level without causing an undue increase in hardness or alkalinity. The results are tabulated in the following table.

In each of the cases the pH slightly rose up. The pH increase helps recarbonation by lessening the amount of CO₂ needed. pH and alkalinity do not correspond linearly in the tabulated results. This is to be expected as pH is a measure of only H⁺ or OH⁻ concentration while alkalinity takes into account all ions such as OH⁻, CO₃²⁻, HCO₃⁻ and also free CO₂.

Except with sample no. 2 the hardness has not appreciably changed during coagulation. Karaikudi has laterite soil within a few feet depth and in some regions even on the surface. The composition of the soil also varies within a few metres as gauged by the iron content of the laterite. This fact partly explains the non-conformity of sample No. 2 with others in the context of hardness.

Dosage of MgCO₃ is much less than the dosage of alum. The dosage of alum for soft surface waters has been determined by Culp and Culp³ as 20 mg/l. The samples taken up for investigation in the present work are soft as per specifications laid down by the American Water Works Association in 1968⁴. Thus the sample consumes less of MgCO₃ than it would consume alum which is incidentally costlier than MgCO₃.

The work regarding determination of effective pH range for coagulation is under progress.

Experimental

The experimental method followed by us is given

in Chemistry for Sanitary Engineers, Sawyer and McCarty⁵. 300 ml of the sample was taken in a glass jar. Suspensions of MgCO₃ (1 ml = 2.5 mg) and Ca(OH)₂ (1 ml = 1.8 mg) were prepared. The desired amount of coagulant was added to the sample with vigorous stirring. Then the sample was flocculated for 45 min on a paddle stirrer. The sample was allowed to stand and the clear water was analysed for turbidity, pH, hardness and alkalinity. (For turbidity measurements, photo-electric turbidity meter by Toshniwal Instruments, was used).

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Preparation of a Liquid Polysulfide Polymer for Leather Impregnation

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ONE of the most important industrial leathers viz., oil seal leathers is used for a wide variety of purposes in aeroplanes, automobiles and elsewhere as pneumatic or hydraulic packings that are subjected to high pressures and frictional endurance such as air-brakes and hydraulic rams. These leathers should not harden up in hot oil, must be capable of being moulded so that they retain their shape and flexibility at elevated as well as low temperatures. The main property imparted by the impregnant is resistance to hot air, water and hot oils under high pressure as high as 10.5 Kg/cm² and temperatures ranging from 53.9 to 121.1^{°C}.

The common impregnating agents such as tallow and waxes will not stand these stringent requirements resulting in failure of specimens.

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The right type of impregnating materials developed for such industrial uses are polysulfide liquid polymers such as LP-2, LP-3, LP-8, etc.² Processes for preparations of such liquid polymers are covered by patents and the conditions of preparation uncertain.

In the present work, a liquid polysulfide polymer suitable for leather impregnation was obtained by condensation of bis-2-chloroethyl formal and sodium polysulfide³ and its chemical structure determined.

The bis-2-chloroethyl formal was prepared by the condensation of purified and distilled ethylene chlorohydrine (B.P. 125-129°) with 37% formaldehyde (LR B.D.H.) and removing water as an azeotrope with xylene, for 2.5 hours. The formation of the formal proceeds very readily, catalysed by the residual acidity present in chlorohydrin, nearly to completion.

Residual xylene was distilled off under vacuum and the product neutralised with gaseous ammonia.

Sodium sulfide (commercial) was heated in twice the amount of water, cooled and centrifuged. To the heated clear solution, sulfur powder (75% on the weight of sodium sulfide) was added slowly with stirring, heated for 30 minutes and again centrifuged to give sodium polysulfide.

Bis-2-chloroethyl formal was heated over boiling water and sodium polysulfide solution was added slowly with stirring (Bis-2-chloroethyl formal: sodium polysulfide 9:10 by weight). 0.1% of tetrachloroethane was also added as a cross-linking agent. 50% of water was added and heating continued.

NMR Spectrum of Bis-2-Chloroethyl formal

NMR SPECTRUM OF EC-1000

After about 25 hours, the initially existed two layers disappeared, forming one layer with sediments. Heating was further continued till a highly viscous pitch settled down, with minimum amount of aqueous layer.

The contents were washed with water to ensure complete removal of sodium chloride and other water soluble products formed.

The polymer layer was then extracted with dichloroethane. Finally dichloroethane was evaporated or distilled off to give a viscous polymer.

The polymer obtained (named EC-1000) thus was very clean and could be stored indefinitely.

The structure of this polymer and its precursor were ascertained by consideration of their spectral properties.

In the infra-red spectrum, bis-2-chloroethyl formal(I), the precursor for EC-1000, shows absorptions at wavelengths given in Table 1. This together with the NMR spectrum where the signals appear at δ 4.67 (s, 2 pr) and two doublets at δ 3.70 and 3.63 ($\delta=7$ Hz each) provides conclusive evidence for the assigned structure (I).

The spectral data of the polymer are very much similar to those of Thiokol LP-3 (Thiokol Corporation, USA). The details of infra-red absorptions are given in Table 1. In the NMR spectrum, the methylene dioxy group appears as a singlet at δ 4.78, the S-H absorption as a broad singlet between δ 4.40-4.60 (exchangeable with D_2O).

TABLE-1

	Infra-red absorption frequency (wave number cm^{-1})	assignment
Monomer- Bis-2-chloroethyl formal	2780 shoulder	O-CH ₂ -O
	1450 strong	CH ₂ -O def.
	1470 strong	OH ₂ -Cl def.
	1370 medium	C-C skeletal
	1290 strong	CH ₂ wag
	1155 strong	C-O stretch
	1120 broad	C-O stretch
	745 broad and strong	C-Cl stretch
Polymer EC-1000	2780 medium	O-CH ₂ -O
	1460 strong	CH ₂ -O def.
	1410 strong	CH ₂ -S def.
	1370 strong	C-C skeletal
	1280 strong	CH ₂ wag
	1155 strong	C-O st.
	1120 broad	O-CH ₂ -O
	710 strong	C-S st.
	670 broad	C-S st.
490 broad	S-S st.	

The methylene absorptions present quite interesting features. While the methylene protons adjacent to oxygen generate the usual triplet at δ 3.97, the CH₂, α to polysulfide unit appear as a complex pattern situated between δ 2.80-3.40. This diastereotopic nature of these methylene protons points to a strong perturbation by the polysulfide unit in EC-1000 and provide added support for the assigned structure (II), for EC-1000.

Further work is underway in fully characterising this polymer with respect to molecular weight, etc. Initial results on the application of the polymer on leathers show encouraging results.

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Gravimetric Determination of Copper(II) with Anilinium Tetraisothiocyanatodanilinechromate(III)

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It has been found that tetraisothiocyanatodanilinechromate(III) anion forms a stable, crystalline and easily filterable compound with copper(II), molecular weight being 1072.62 (gravimetric factor 0.0592).

Experimental

Anilinium tetraisothiocyanatodanilinechromate (III): The reagent was prepared by the method

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